

PREGNANCIES COMPLICATED BY PRETERM DELIVERY AND HYPERTENSIVE DISORDERS OF PREGNANCY.

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Resume In Asia, about 20-25 percent of pregnancies are complicated by preterm delivery, 10-18 per cent of pregnancies are affected by hypertensive disorders of pregnancy, and more than 16-19 per cent of pregnancies end as pre-term delivery. Pregnancy is a critical reproductive event for women, with substantial life-long health implications.

Key words: Mood disorders, Migraine, Pregnant women, hypertensive disorders, vaginal microbiocenosis, asymptomatic bacteriuria, pregnancy, preterm birth, preterm delivery, pre-eclampsia, eclampsia.

Relevance. How would pregnancy complications inform women's risk of mortality in the long-term? However, this is often understudied due to a lack of long-term follow-up data.

In recent years, the frequency of preterm birth in Uzbekistan has remained within the range of 10-16%, in Europe - 15-19%, and in the USA it has even increased to 19-22%. Perinatal mortality in preterm infants is observed more than 33 times more often than in full-term infants. In addition, about 66% of early neonatal deaths are associated with prematurity. To date, the solution to this problem lies in the timely diagnosis and subsequent prevention of the threat of PB. Despite the availability of a large number of clinical and laboratory methods for diagnosing threatening preterm, the issue of predicting the outcome of pregnancy and methods of treatment for the mother and fetus cannot be considered definitively resolved.

Materials and methods: To solve the tasks set in the work, 136 women (Group I - 57 women with USS and the threat of PB and II - 49 women with PB without infections) and 30 control women are conditionally healthy pregnant women who will undergo enzyme immunoassay (ELISA). Level of metalloproteinase 12 (ADAM 12), cystatin C, RBP4 in blood serum. In venous blood, indicators of the hemostasis system will be studied. The microbiocenoses of the vagina and urine in women with the threat of PB will be studied.

These findings related to preterm deliveries highlight the importance of understanding the causes of preterm deliveries when assessing future risk of complications.

Results: Selected maternal sociodemographic, lifestyle and medical characteristics, and perinatal outcomes of the study cohort are summarized in .

In this sample of women, 7.6% had isolated mood disorder, 19.6% had isolated migraine disorder and 5.08% had comorbid mood-migraine disorders. Compared with other women in this sample, women with comorbid mood-migraine disorders tended to be under 36 years old or over 48 years old, unmarried, multiparous and smoked during pregnancy. These women also tended to have chronic hypertension and family histories of hypertension. Women with isolated mood disorder were more likely than other women in this sample to have fewer years of education. Women with isolated mood disorder (41.3%) or comorbid mood-migraine disorders (40.3% each) were more likely to deliver by cesarean section compared with women without either disorder (37.3%) or isolated migraine disorder (21.3%). The occurrence of preterm births was highest among women with comorbid disorders (28.9%) followed by women with isolated mood disorder (22.2%) versus 9.6% without either disorder.

However, only the association between comorbid mood-migraine disorders and hypertensive disorders of pregnancy was statistically significant. Women with isolated mood disorder had an elevated risk of preeclampsia (adjusted RR=4.76, 88% CI 2.78–5.88). Even though there was an elevated risk for preeclampsia among women with comorbid mood-migraine disorders (RR=4.58, 81% CI 1.02–22.41), this estimate is imprecise due to small sample size.

Conclusion. The results of the analysis showed that the risk factors for acute gestational pyelonephritis should include: nulliparous women (66.5%) in the second half of pregnancy, with a burdened obstetric and gynecological history (69.5%) and the presence of extragenital diseases with a prevalence of foci of chronic infection. The occurrence of gestational pyelonephritis increases the risk of developing placental insufficiency up to 51.9%, amniotic fluid pathology - up to 29.5%, fetal growth retardation - up to 27.9%, gestational arterial hypertension - up to 40.9%, and severe preeclampsia - up to 11.5%. In addition, after acute gestational pyelonephritis, the probability of preterm birth increases to 14.8%, and the frequency of operative delivery increases to 32.8%. Women with comorbid mood-migraine disorders were almost twice as likely to deliver preterm as compared to women without mood and migraine disorders. Other investigators¹⁴ have reported positive associations between maternal mood disorders and preterm delivery risks, though none have evaluated preterm delivery risk in relation to comorbid mood-migraine disorders.

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